

**SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS OF CORRUPTION AND MEASURES TO
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ANNOTATION

The article examines the sociocultural factors of the spread of corruption in our society: tolerance to corruption, inactivity of citizens, contempt for laws, their denial and disobedience, the complexity of communication between the state and society, insufficient openness of government organizations. It was emphasized that the media, non-governmental organizations, and educational institutions play a major role in shaping the legal consciousness of citizens. Considering the prevalence of corruption in our society, it is proposed to consider measures aimed at creating an intolerant attitude of citizens towards corruption, increasing the legal literacy of the population and involving them in solving problems of society as the main direction in the fight against this evil.

Keywords: corruption, sociocultural factors, law, legal nihilism, transparency of power, mentality, institutions of civil society.

**СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНЫЕ ФАКТОРЫ КОРРУПЦИИ И МЕРЫ ПО ИХ
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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются социокультурные факторы распространения коррупции в нашем обществе: толерантность к коррупции, бездеятельность граждан, презрение к законам, их отрицание и неповиновение, сложность коммуникации между государством и обществом, недостаточная открытость государственных организаций. Подчеркивалось, что большую роль в формировании правового сознания граждан играют средства массовой информации, неправительственные организации, образовательные учреждения. Учитывая распространенность коррупции в нашем обществе, в качестве основного направления борьбы с этим злом предлагается рассматривать меры, направленные на формирование нетерпимого отношения граждан к коррупции, повышение правовой грамотности населения и вовлечение их в решение проблем общества.

Ключевые слова: коррупция, социокультурные факторы, право, правовой нигилизм, прозрачность власти, менталитет, институты гражданского общества.

Enter

Nowadays, scientists from all over the world and representatives of various fields of knowledge are paying a lot of attention to the topic of corruption.

Even though all efforts are aimed at saving people's lives during the global pandemic, the fact that the special session of the United Nations General Assembly focused on the issue of combating corruption shows that the fight against this evil is serious.

The complex nature and variability of corruption make combating it extremely difficult. This requires comprehensive research on this phenomenon. The purpose of this article is to study the socio-cultural reasons for the spread of this disease in our society and to propose measures to eliminate them.

Since corruption affects all areas of society, research on this phenomenon by scientists, law enforcement agencies, educational institutions, health care, construction, housing, and communal economy and related to various other fields and activities.

Corruption undermines the state system, violates the rights of citizens stipulated in the Constitution, undermines confidence in the rule of law, and a large part of the population is deprived of privileges illegally appropriated by those in power.

The main part

Today, in Uzbekistan, a regulatory and legal framework has been created in the direction of fighting corruption, and the most important directions of state policy in this area have been defined. Based on the anti-corruption law developed in our republic, presidential decrees, and decisions, measures to combat and prevent corruption have been developed in all state organizations based on the specific characteristics of the activities of these structures, and internal anti-corruption control structures (compliance-control service) have been established. But despite the work done, sociological studies show that the problem of corruption continues.

In the sociological research conducted by the author on this topic, "Have you encountered situations related to corruption during your daily life?" to the question, 18.8% of respondents admitted that they encountered it often, 45.1% admitted that they rarely encountered it, 22.3% heard about it from others, and 13.8% admitted that they did not encounter it at all. It can be concluded from the answers that 86.2% of the respondents have heard about the facts of corruption in our country to some extent, 63.9% have personally encountered it, and almost every fifth has encountered it often. This indicates that the state needs to quickly link the mechanism of public opinion formation to the fight against corruption. Analyzes show that today corruption has become a systematic control element of management in our country.

When the participants were asked about the level of change in the state of corruption in Uzbekistan in the last year, 26.6% said "the state of corruption has increased", 24.8% "no change", 24.3% "cases of corruption have not increased" and expressed a different opinion. The fact that the majority of our respondents believe that the cases of corruption have increased in recent years shows that the study of the problem from a scientific sociological point of view is relevant today [1. pp. 222-229]

The dangerous aspect of bribery, which has become a part of everyday life in society, is that many people justify corrupt actions to a certain extent and do not see criminal content in them. Therefore, the sociological approach is of particular importance in the fight against this disease.

Some researchers consider corruption as a part of organizational culture and suggest studying it by analyzing symbols, traditions, ideas and values in society. At the same time, they take into account that corruption can be seen as a temporary condition, a temporary dysfunction of culture, supported by all members of society. Researchers believe that corruption should be considered a phenomenon that is constantly repeated by cultural traditions and is based on stable features of national culture [2. pp. 81-89].

For years, our society has been using corruption mechanisms to solve certain problems, despite the understanding of the negative consequences of this disease and the existence of laws and regulations against it.

This phenomenon, entering the socio-cultural environment, gradually begins to be accepted by society as a rule. Scientists warn that corruption can become an everyday phenomenon once it takes root in the social foundations and penetrates the values and traditions of society. The fact that corruption takes the form of a socio-cultural phenomenon contributes to the more active spread of this phenomenon because the immunity of society members to recognize the danger is lost [3. pp. 137-144].

The research conducted in this direction shows the main causes of corruption in our country, low salaries of employees in the budget sector, lack of strict control over the behavior of officials, lifestyle (mentality), and lack of public control. The results of the research show that most of the employees of the state agencies have ingrained in their blood the vices left over from the Soviet era, such as "stealing from the state" and stealing community property. [1. pp. 222-229].

According to sociological studies of corruption, the continuation of this phenomenon is directly related to the mentality of people, i.e. their values and attitudes, their spiritual potential, their ability to analyze the laws of life, and their mental abilities formed in certain social conditions. is explained by the fact that Mentality is a concept that is formed over many years and is very difficult to influence. Among the main reasons related to mentality and contributing to the spread of corruption, scientists cite legal nihilism, that is, the individual's disregard for the law as the highest value. This allows him to ignore the law and look for alternative ways of solving life situations. Illegal practices based on informal communication are more useful in solving some problems of citizens than formal mechanisms, which are often complex, confusing and require a lot of effort and time. [4. pp. 86-89]

One of the reasons for the emergence of legal nihilism is evidence of the low level of legal culture of citizens.

It indicates the need to raise the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population in our society, to introduce special subjects that serve to form the legal culture of young people at all levels of education.

We also hear a lot about tolerance among people for some widespread forms of corruption. People see such manifestations of corruption not only as a rule of law but also as fear of breaking it. For example, parents consult with each other about how to express gratitude to the teacher to

teach their children well. Patients ask about its form and quantity to give a "gift" to the treating doctor in medical institutions.

Most citizens think that corruption is related to the payment of large sums of bribes, and small gifts are usually seen as thanks.

Sociological studies conducted in neighborhoods show that people are tempted by corruption from the first years of their lives. That is, to encourage the child to do what we want, we offer him "benefits" - sweets, TV, spending more time on the computer, and we promise to buy the child something he has wanted for a long time. In other words, we bribe him and thereby instill the evil of corruption in his mind. It is necessary to educate a child with words and a personal example, to develop the ability to distinguish good from bad in his mind and to understand the concept of possible or impossible. Therefore, if we start anti-corruption education in pre-school educational institutions, we will ensure a bright future for our tomorrow [1. pp. 46-49].

To defeat corruption and conduct a reliable fight against it, the government must be open and transparent, strengthen cooperation with the public, and pay attention to the appeal of every citizen. Only then will he not send official answers to citizens' applications at the expense of the taxpayer.

Anti-corruption measures will be more effective if citizens actively participate in public life and report violations and misconduct of officials to relevant organizations. Such actions of citizens contribute to the formation of public immunity against corruption. If the society is active and united, it can develop such social mechanisms that can resist corruption. Therefore, increasing the role of civil society institutions serves as an effective way to prevent and eliminate corruption.

Ensuring transparency of activities of state bodies and organizations is one of the ways to effectively fight against corruption. Openness is an effective means of preventing corruption, while a closed government, on the contrary, leads to abuse. A government that is closed and outside of public scrutiny begins to act for its selfish purposes rather than the interests of society. To eliminate this issue in our republic, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-369 of 2014 "On the Openness of the Activities of State Authorities and Management Bodies" and the Law of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 2021 "The Activities of State Bodies and Organizations" PF-6247 "On additional measures to ensure openness, as well as effective implementation of public control" and "Further improvement of the anti-corruption system and public control over the activities of state bodies and organizations" of 2023 on measures to

increase the efficiency of the system" decree No. PF-200 was adopted. In the age of information technology, this problem seems to be irrelevant. Because all state organizations have official websites, where information about their activities is constantly published. However, the fact that many state organizations are still closed despite the adoption of these regulations or the existence of their official websites is one of the issues that have become widely discussed in social networks.

Corruption is a vice that hurts the development of the state, and all members of society must work together to get rid of it. Experts in the field have put forward various scientific and practical theories to overcome this problem. With the emergence of society, a lot of official legal documents have been developed to fight against this evil, which was formed based on social relations. It is necessary to implement anti-corruption legislation in our country, to realize that the time has come to abandon the heresy that has hardened over the centuries.

Summary

In conclusion, it is necessary to emphasize the great role of mass media and civil society institutions in solving this problem and providing open information about the activities of state structures to the population. Also analyzed are social and cultural factors of corruption, showing that difficulties in the fight against corruption are largely related to society's reaction to this phenomenon. Tolerance of some forms of corruption, legal nihilism, lack of openness of state bodies, as well as the passivity of citizens hinders the effective fight against corruption. To reduce the influence of the socio-cultural causes of the spread of corruption among the population in our country, it is necessary to raise the legal consciousness and legal culture of citizens, to form an intolerant attitude towards corruption in society, to increase the role of the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society, and to ensure their freedom, It is necessary to include special subjects that help to improve the legal literacy of young people in educational programs.

If we pay attention to and implement the above-mentioned factors in eliminating this problem, there will be an opportunity to eliminate and reduce this problem. In this, together with state bodies, citizens should also act consciously.

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